

Muslims Perception about Islam Phobia, Hostility, Prejudiced and Discrimination against Muslims in European Countries

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Abstract

The 21st century had seen a scenario extraordinary to Muslims, including initiatives to build mosques and minarets and impose burqa prohibitions. The study's primary aim was to explore the "Muslims" opinion about key factors that are the reasons against 'Islamization'. A self-made questionnaire was developed and validated through pilot testing with a reliability index of .80 was send to respondents through online services. After data collection, SPSS was used for data analysis, showing that 89% of respondents believe that media is not playing their role and biased media spreading anti-Muslim's news. 67% agreed that the coward leaders of Muslims are the root cause of all this hostility against Muslims. 90% of respondents said publishing cartoons in Denmark about Prophet Muhammed (PBUH) is hostile against Muslims. However, no difference is found in participants opinions based on demographics. This study also concludes that the world must stop the physical and verbal attacks on Muslims, and international media must positively play their role.

Keywords: Islam, Islamophobia, hostility, prejudice, discrimination, racism, sentiments.

Introduction

Muslims have been present in Western countries for hundreds of years. However, no signs of Muslim settlement could be found. Because of World War II labour shortages, many Muslims from the British Commonwealth came to work in the UK (Hussain 2008).

With the ethnoreligious and community disputes, hunger, and natural catastrophes, the number of Muslims fleeing their homes rose. Refugees came from all over the world, including Somalia, East Africa, and the Middle East. However, in the 1990s, a new wave of asylum seekers arrived, including Bosnian Muslims, Kosovo Kurds, and Afghans. Because of British colonialism, the vast majority of British Muslims are descended from people from South Asia. In Britain until the 1980s, Muslims were viewed primarily as members of a communal religious group rather than as ethnics and countries in general. To a certain extent, this is attributable to the British public's decreasing regard for religion in general (Hussain, 2008).

However, as non-European-origin populations grew in number in the United Kingdom, the importance was placed on religious activity. Minority groups were often obliged to restructure their religious practises to access public resources and sustain their religious efforts (Merry, 2004). Islamophobia began in the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries when it became quite popular (Bravo Lopez, 2011).

Runnymede's conceptual approach indicates that Islamophobia may be viewed as a latent entity with numerous aspects. This description encompasses concepts like otherness, inferiority, and anti-Islamic sentiment, supporting the idea that Islamophobia is only a repackaged version of religious prejudice. According to popular belief, Islam is a monolithic movement that is inflexible and resistive to change. When it comes to the West, Islam is viewed as 'other' and is considered inferior. It is also perceived as violent and misogynistic. Islam is associated with violence, aggression, and a sense of menace, and it is viewed as a religion that encourages terrorism. In political and military circles, Islam is viewed as a political philosophy. Islam's criticisms of the West are dismissed as unfounded (Marranci, 2004).

Ciftci (2012) studies that there are several factors of anti-Islamic sentiments in Western nations. Discussing Islamophobia should begin with a general hatred of Muslims, then proceed to violence and terrorism as a result.

Literature Review

According to this concept, competition for such resources can promote discrimination, prejudice, and even war between rival groups where resources are scarce. As Muslims make up a substantial number of Western immigrants, realistic conflict theory and a realistic perceived danger can be used to explain anti-Muslim feelings in the West. Many Westerners believed that Muslims were complicit in al Qaeda's actions and attacks. Because Muslims are seen as a danger to Westerners' physical wellbeing and cultural values, Westerners see them as fanatical, aggressive, and terrorist-supportive (McLaren, 2003).

From a philosophical standpoint, it asserts that Western liberal Islamophobia results from a skewed view of secularization that excludes a religion like Islam. Anti-Muslim prejudice, according to him, has something to do with Western society's inability to embrace diversity. The word can also mean a negative attitude or action toward Muslims (Dekker et al., 2011).

Hostility toward Muslims is usual or expected. Runnymede's conceptual approach indicates that Islamophobia may be viewed as a latent entity with numerous aspects. This description encompasses concepts like otherness, inferiority, and anti-Islamic sentiment, supporting the idea that Islamophobia is only a repackaged version of religious prejudice. Islam is perceived as a monolithic bloc, resistant to change and stagnant, is considered different and "other," and is seen below the West as barbaric, irrational, primitive, and sexist Islam. (Marranci, 2004).

Nielsen (1999) aim to increase interest in Islamic culture at the grass-roots level through 'information offensive' based on cultural, intellectual, and educational efforts, complemented by a variety of inter-religious and intercultural awareness events. Examples of media attempts to deconstruct errors and stereotypes, as well as to cooperate with scholars and Muslim groups, were highlighted.

Zero rejection and equal right to each is a hot issue that must be maintained even if doing so does not immediately impact us personally. It is not enough that the discrimination which directly affects people or groups should simply be combated. To comprehend and respond to specific types of racism, it is fair and justifiable to understand and respond to anti-Jewish, anti-Muslim, or anti-black racism. However,

broad anti-racist human rights and equality perspective means also sticking out for other marginalized groups discriminated against (Marion, 2014).

A 2015 French Court Decision¹ that failed to take account in public schools of Muslim dietary restrictions is a serious warning to the effect that increasing Islamophobia threatens religious freedom in modern Europe. Last year, the mayor announced that, despite the existence of an important Muslim population and the rules preventing kids from bringing pickled luncheons to school, his neighbourhood school cafeterias would no longer provide children pork alternatives (Esposito and & Mogahed 2007).

Angered by the order, a Muslim community filed a lawsuit seeking injunctive relief to prevent its youngsters from being forced to choose between eating pork or going without food (Abdelkader, 2017).

According to AfD's website, it was formed in 2013 as an anti-immigrant political party. Its leaders argue that Islam is incompatible with the German constitution. As a result, the government must take measures to halt Muslim immigration and either integrate or eliminate the country's current Muslim population. Many Germans, according to research, have unfavourable views towards Muslims furthermore because German anti-Islam rallies are being opposed by Christian clerics (Tesler, 2018).

Islam is viewed as a monolithic group that is static or inconsistent in changing the number of hate crimes documented by law against Muslim's enforcement in 2013 increased by 11.3% over the previous year, according to the US State Department. 102 The number of anti-Muslim hate crimes has significantly grown (Poole et al., 2021).

Research Objectives

- To Examine the opinion of Muslims against anti-Muslim sentiments, hate, discrimination crimes.
- The excessive role of media reporting to enhance hate, hostility and prejudice against Muslims
- Find out the root cause of anti-Muslim hate, and prejudice against Muslims?

Research Questions

- What is the opinion of Muslims against anti-Muslim sentiments, hate, discrimination crimes?
- What is the role of media reporting to enhance hate, hostility and prejudice against Muslims?
- What is the root cause of anti-Muslim hate and prejudice against Muslims?

Methodology

Research Design

The research design for this study was quantitative. The study's major purpose is to determine the opinion of Muslims against anti-Muslim sentiments, hate, discrimination crimes. The research design for this study is survey research. The researcher uses a quantitative method and questionnaire to collect information.

Population

Every Muslim and educated person in Multan city constituted the population for this study.

Sampling

Due to the huge number of populations for this study Simple, Convenient sampling technique was used as our research was not restricted to any specific area.

Sampling probability

The questionnaire was forward to 110 respondents through email and WhatsApp link from which 100 absolute respondents' response to our questionnaire. The probability of sampling was about 90%.

Instrument of the study

A self-made questionnaire was developed with three sections. The first section contains preliminary information about respondents, 2nd section contains Factors Predicting Hostility, Prejudiced and Discrimination against other Muslims in European Countries, and 3rd section Reasons of prejudice and social discrimination. The questionnaire was developed on 5 Likert scales. Scoring of the data was as 5 points were given to "strongly agree", 4 points were given to "agree", 3 points were given to "undecided", 2 points were given to "disagree", and 1 point was given to "strongly disagree".

Data collection & analysis

Data was collected through online services by using Google forms due to the privilege of covid-19 in Pakistan. Data were interpreted, and analysis was done on SPSS. Statistical tools such as ANOVA, t-Test, percentage, mean, and stander deviation were used for data analysis and presented in the tables

Table 1
Demographic Analysis of Respondents

Sr#	Respondents	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Gender			
1	Female	30	30%
2	Male	70	70%
	Total	100	100
Working experience			
1	1-5 years	42	42%
2	5-10 years	24	24%
3	10-15 years	30	30%
4	15 above	4	4%
	Total	100	100
Qualification			
1	Master	80	80%
2	M.Phil.	20	20%
	Total	100	100

Table 1 illustrates that 70% of the respondents were male, and 30 % were female. 80% of respondents have master degrees. 42% of respondents had working experience of 1-5 years.

Table 2

Statistical technique Independent Sample t. test was used to compare the responses of the respondent at the basis of Gender

Gender	N	Mean	SD	Df	Sig.
Male	30	97.94	8.93	50	.03
Female	70	96.28	5.68		

Table 2 illustrates that the t-value is less than the significance value, so there is a significant difference based on Gender.

Table 3

Statistical technique Independent Sample t. test was used to compare the responses of the respondent at the basis of Qualification

Qualification	N	Mean	SD	Df	Sig.
Master	80	96.00	6.94	50	.42
M. Phil.	20	99.33	5.38		

Statistical technique independent t-test was applied at the Qualification to compare the opinions of respondents. The table illustrates that the significant value is .42, which is greater than the standard value of .05; it shows no difference between Master and M.Phil. respondents.

Table 4

One Way ANOVA test was used to compare the responses of the respondent at the basis of Experience

Experience	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	106.16	6	35.39	.78	.52
Within Groups	2197.06	93	45.78		
Total	2303.22	99			

**P > .05 Level of Significance*

The table illustrates that the significance value of .515 is greater than the stander value of 0.5, so statistically, no difference is found in teachers' opinions based on working Experience.

Results

The following result was concluded based on data analysis.

Table 5

Reasons of Hostility, Prejudiced and Discrimination against other Muslims in European Countries:

Sr.#	Question	SA (%)	A (%)	UD (%)	DA (%)	SDA (%)	M	SD
1	Islamophobia exists in almost every country in the world	60%	25%	3%	2%	10%	2.72	0.68
2	Racism is not restricted to any country. A diverse range of people feels it daily based on Gender, race, religion and culture.	31%	54%	6%	9%	0%	3.91	0.91
3	Policies of the government in Europe have not guaranteed equal rights for all Muslims in particular	41%	45%	10%	17	20%	3.93	0.73
4	xenophobic, populist parties rising across Europe have been nurturing the notion of continuous European "Islamization" or invasion.	28%	27%	10%	30%	4%	3.34	1.28

5	The events of 9 November altered public sentiment dramatically against Muslims	22%	51%	17%	7%	3%	3.71	1.01
6	Growing the sentiments against Muslims is planned by narrow-minded people.	21%	48%	16%	13%	2%	3.67	1.06
7	I believe that freedom of religion is born right to every person in this world.	25%	57%	3%	14%	1%	4.05	0.95

Table 6
Factors Predicting Hostility, Prejudiced and Discrimination against other Muslims in European Countries:

Sr.#	Question	SA (%)	A (%)	UD (%)	DA (%)	SDA (%)	M	SD
8	The attack against Muslims' property, places of religious worship and a conspicuous representation of their religious identities such as ladies wearing hijab or niqab	32%	59%	4%	2%	3%	3.9	0.98
9	online threats of violence, defamation and abuse.	29%	55%	7%	7%	2%	3.2	1.28
10	Policies or laws that impact Muslims indirectly or excessively	24%	29%	16%	23%	8%	4.27	1.07
11	Education, job, living and access to goods and services are discriminatory	52%	39%	4%	3%	2%	4.06	1
12	Profiling and police ethnicity and religious issues, including several anti-terrorism measures	36%	54%	8%	2%	0%	4.18	1.12
13	Some journalists and politicians — across the full spectrum — have public statements that stigmatize Muslims as a group and overlook their beneficial contributions to their communities and nations	51%	38%	5%	2%	4%	3.6	1.1
14	Unawareness of Muslims from main Islamic teaching is a reason for hostility	32%	36%	15%	13%	4%	4.12	0.95

Table 7
Reasons for prejudice and social discrimination

Sr.#	Question	SA (%)	A (%)	UD (%)	DA (%)	SDA (%)	M	SD
15	Do you think that keeping Pakistan on the red list while India is out of the list, which has a great	29%	54%	9%	6%	2%	3.18	1.30

	prevalence of covid 19, is a type of prejudice against Muslims?								
16	Do you think that non-acceptance of the 'Talban' govt in their own country while accepting Jew's govt in Israel is prejudice against Muslims?	24%	28%	18%	22%	8%	4.25	1.09	
	Do you think publishing cartoons in Denmark about Prophet Muhammed (PBUH) is hostile against Muslims?								
17	Islamophobia is all due to corrupt and biased media spreading anti-Muslim's news.	36%	53%	10%	1%	0%	4.16	1.14	
18	Islamophobia is a poisonous weapon that international media use to get cheap fame.	51%	37%	7%	1%	4%	3.58	1.12	
19	The coward leaders of Muslims are the root cause of all this hostility against Muslims	32%	35%	17%	12%	4%	4.10	0.97	
20	The contemporary academic narrative fails to address the problem because they do not consider the Islamic perspective fully.	38%	48%	6%	0%	8%	3.93	1.24	
21	Bridging the gaps in different religions can be only possible when everyone is considered equal.	38%	52%	9%	0%	1%	3.38	1.23	
22	The poor social-economic status of Muslims is the root cause of discrimination against Muslims.	27%	38%	12%	18%	5%	3.78	1.22	
23	Islam hostility is used to explain discrimination against Muslims and the exclusion of Muslims from mainstream culture.	32%	53%	6%	2%	7%	3.78	1.02	
24	Islam is seen as separate and 'other' because it has the power to dominate the world.	24%	59%	10%	6%	1%	3.8	1.07	
25	The media do not use Muslims in Muslim nations because they believe they endanger their physical wellbeing, as a fan, violent and terrorist	29%	58%	8%	2%	3%	3.30	1.10	

Findings

Our finding illustrates that more than 80% of respondents believe that Islamophobia exists in almost every country in the world, not only in Europe. 73% of participants agreed that the 9/11 terrorist attacks drastically changed public opinion towards Muslims. More than 80% of people face Online threats of violence, defamation, and abuse against Muslims. While talking about Reasons for prejudice and social discrimination, 84% agreed to the statement Islam is seen as separate and 'other' because it has the power to dominate the world. 84% believe that keeping Pakistan on the red list while India is out of the list, which has a great prevalence of covid 19, is prejudice

against Muslims. When we discuss the role of media, 88% of Muslims think that Islamophobia is a poisonous weapon that international media use to get cheap fame. 87% agreed that feeling exploited by media view in none Muslim countries is Muslims as fanatical, violent and supportive of terrorism because they perceive them to threaten their physical wellbeing. 89% of Muslims said all due to corrupt and biased media spreading anti-Muslim's news. 52% of respondents agreed that non-acceptance of 'Talban' govt in their own country while accepting Jew's govt in Israel shows prejudice and discrimination against Muslims. 92% of respondents state that publishing cartoons in Denmark about Prophet Muhammed (PBUH) is not hostility against Muslims, which should be stopped.

Discussion

While discussing the current issues of Islamophobia, prejudice and hostility against Muslims, it is concluded that Muslims in Europe are segregated and discriminated against based on their religion. Islamophobia exists in almost every country in the world. According to the poll, one in four individuals also holds unfavourable opinions towards Muslims in Britain and the United States (Pew Research Center, 2008). In this matter, the media does not play a constructive role 86 percent thought that the government's policies in Europe had not guaranteed equal rights for all Muslims, in particular. Eighty-eight percent believed that Islamophobia is a toxic weapon used by worldwide media to get cheap fame. In the West is unparalleled Islamophobia. Haste and bias towards Muslims during discussions is the fundamental cause of anti-Muslim hate. Eighty-five percent of the respondents believe that anti-muslim hate crime tries to split the world into two homogenous groups, 'us' and them,' while failing to admit the wider spreading of Muslims, justifying discrimination against Muslims and excluding Muslims from mainstream society (Fekete, 2004).

Many respondents think the lack of knowledge of the Islamic teachings by Muslims is a motive for antagonism, which means that the actual Islamic cultural expression needs an hour. The Islamic Commission on Human Rights has proposed to create an Islamic curriculum that enables the citizens to realize the right to religious and cultural expression alongside the mainstream curriculum, thereby enhancing societies as political spaces (Sari, 2020). The events included targeting mosques, Muslim women who had hijab or niqab, in London, who suffered a terrible acid assault (headscarf) and two Muslims (Khan, 2018).

Further Recommendations

1. The government should reintroduce policies against discrimination against wider anti-Muslim's strategies.
2. There should be international strategies to control inequalities in education, employment and criminal justice.

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